

**Jane Winters,
Professor of Digital
Humanities and
Director of the Digital
Humanities Research
Hub, University of
London**

Open access enhances the research process

– Jane Winters

Open access is good for research and good for researchers. It encourages scholarly practice, diverse perspectives and interdisciplinary working.

Open access publishing enables academics to disseminate their work to a larger, more diverse audience. It also means academics can access a larger, more diverse range of research materials.

Speculative reading

Jane Winters is Professor of Digital Humanities and Director of the Digital Humanities Research Hub at the University of London. She says humanities research is increasingly interdisciplinary, requiring academics to access research outside their core area. Speculative reading is very important, leading to a richer research experience and outputs, but university libraries and academics often don't have the funds to purchase extra-curricular material.

Winters says:

“The cost of academic monographs in particular is so high that speculative, out of interest reading is unlikely to happen if it requires purchasing a copy of a book.”

When research is freely and easily available, Winters thinks academics are more likely to engage with speculative reading, on the off chance it might be relevant. If it's expensive and hard to access or find, she says they might think it's not worth the effort.

Diversity of thinking

Open access publishing facilitates collaborations with a wide group of people, encouraging the cross-pollination of ideas, experiences and perspectives. It also helps get research known and cited more quickly, raising the profile, awareness and impact of humanities research.

Winters says it's very important that humanities research is accessible to a wide audience, that academics are engaging with and contributing to public debate and helping to shape discourse. She said:

“ In my field, for example – I'm writing about the impact of artificial intelligence on cultural heritage – you want the people who are designing artificial intelligence systems to know about humanities work on bias and ethics. If it's locked away, they're not going to encounter it.

By working and publishing openly, Winters says academics are able to engage with a more diverse set of voices during the whole research process. These voices feed into the research, informing the findings and output.

Benefits to early career scholars

Early career researchers are often advised against publishing open access, with senior academics saying prestige publishing will advance their career more quickly and lead to tenure. But Winters says prestige publishing is not a proxy for quality – open access can be just as good quality.

For a couple of years, Winters was editor of an early career researcher book series called New Historical Perspectives, which does not charge open access costs. She says publishing open access worked very well for them.

“ The early career researchers benefitted enormously from the attention their open access books got. And they were able to cross-promote each other’s work, building a real community around that. It was really effective in career development terms – I think open access is terrific for people early on in their career.